

A phenomenological model for plasma-assisted combustion with NRP discharges in methane-air mixtures: PACMIND

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Abstract

The recent advances in plasma-assisted combustion must now be strengthened through high-fidelity numerical simulations. However, detailed plasma-combustion coupled simulations in complex geometry and turbulent flow involving hundreds of discharges are still unaffordable due to prohibitive computational costs. In this work, a **P**lasma-**A**ssisted **C**ombustion pheno**M**enological model**I**ng for **N**on-equilibrium **D**ischarges (PACMIND) is proposed. The model aims to avoid computing in detail the plasma phase and consists of incorporating the leading order plasma effects on the reactive compressible Navier-Stokes equations. It consists of two ultra-fast effects with radical productions and gas heating, as well as a slower gas heating due to vibrational energy relaxation. Based on detailed kinetic simulations, the model has been applied to air and methane-air mixtures and contains respectively 5 species, 3 reactions and 12 species, 7 reactions. The model has been validated against experiments in air and detailed plasma-assisted combustion ignition simulations in methane-air at various equivalence ratios and reduced electric fields. Significant improvements regarding ignition delay times have been observed by comparison with an existing model. In addition, the model accounts for NO_x production by plasma

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discharge and covers the full range of conditions encountered in a premixed flame. Hence, it opens the way to the simulation of realistic 3D turbulent configurations with minimal over-costs.

Keywords: Plasma Assisted Combustion, Nanosecond Repetitively Pulsed Discharges, Model, Chemistry

1. Introduction

The use of lean mixtures has been promoted in combustion systems to overcome the increasingly restrictive regulations concerning pollutants. In this context, Plasma-Assisted Combustion (PAC) is currently investigated by many groups to address stability and ignition issues. In particular, the use of Nanosecond Repetitively Pulsed (NRP) discharges has shown promising results regarding both flame stabilisation [1, 2] and ignition [3]. These discharges are known to produce both thermal [4] and kinetic [5] effects, leading to an increased efficiency [6, 7].

The recent progress in PAC on realistic configurations have been mainly achieved via experiments. These experimental studies scan a large range of issues, including spray flames [8], diffusion flames [9], lean blowout limits [10], pollutant emissions [11], high pressure swirled flames [12, 13] and flowing ignition [14]. However, the numerical simulation of such problems are highly challenging and therefore quite rare. Indeed, the coupling between the plasma and combustion physics involves a large range of spatial dimensions (*i.e.*, μm to cm) and timescales (*i.e.*, ns to ms). Most of the numerical studies including detailed plasma-combustion kinetics have been restricted to 0D. In [15], the authors improved the standard 0D kinetic modelling by incorporating physical models for diffusion effects, heat transfer, cathode layer and gas dynamics compression/expansion following the discharge [16]. The pressure effects have

been analysed using 0D isochoric adiabatic reactors up to 30 bars in [17], helping to estimate NRPD efficiency for ignition of methane/air and ethylene/air mixtures. One-dimensional simulations have been performed by [18], allowing to model sheath formation close to the electrode boundary, and to evaluate the NRPD effects on ignition as well as premixed and non-premixed flames from the nanosecond to the millisecond timescale. Recently in [19, 20], kinetics reduction techniques as used in the combustion community have been adapted to plasma-chemical mechanisms, allowing to obtain reduced kinetic mechanisms containing around 50 species. Such reduced mechanisms are affordable for fully coupled simulations in 2D-axisymmetric configurations, including the modelling of the discharge propagation, and have been successfully used to study ignition following a single pulse [21] or the effects of electrode geometry and temperature [22]. However, most of the practical uses of NRP discharge require several tens or hundreds of pulses. Very recently, multi-pulses ignition simulations have been achieved in axisymmetric conditions [23, 24]. These studies demonstrated the capability of numerical simulation to correctly predict NRP discharges and to increase the understanding of the underlying processes in canonical configurations at a reasonable cost. Streamer modelling in a 3D environment is extremely challenging and has been addressed recently in [25] using a drift-diffusion model coupled to compressible reactive Navier-Stokes equations in a pin-to-pin configuration. Although computational resources are increasing, plasma-assisted combustion simulations with detailed coupling in realistic 3D turbulent configurations and multiple pulses are still unreachable. This is a major obstacle for complementary experimental and numerical studies required for the future PAC technology advancements.

To overcome this restriction, simplified models may be developed by com-

binning experimental and numerical knowledge. Following this idea, Castela *et al* [26] came up with a phenomenological model reproducing the first order effects of NRP discharges in air-containing reactive mixtures. In this model, the discharge energy is divided into three dominant channels based on the combined studies of [27, 28]: fast (i) kinetic effects and (ii) gas heating followed by (iii) slow gas heating. This model has been used for the LES of a bluff-body turbulent flame stabilisation [29] and flame blow-off cancelling in a sequential burner [30]. However, the kinetic effect of the model is limited to the oxygen molecule dissociation, which is the leading order effect in fresh gases, based on an experiment in air and does not consider the presence of other molecules in the fuel-air mixture or in burnt gases. This is yet a critical point, as in real gas turbines discharges never occur in pure air but rather in the reactants mixture possibly mixed with burnt gas [31, 32, 13]. Indeed, chemical pathways involving atomic oxygen in CH₄-air mixtures can differ from those in pure air as shown in [33]. Improving the plasma chemical effects in burnt gases is even more important as the oxygen molecules disappear, at least partially for lean mixtures. Additionally, it would be very valuable to be able to predict the nitric oxide emission levels, as this is one of the key points in terms of regulations. Moreover, the model can not reflect the influence of the reduced electric field, which is a crucial parameter in the discharge energy branching [1], because the model parameters have been established at a mean reduced electric field around 150 Td.

In the present work, an extended phenomenological PAC model is proposed for methane-air mixtures to take into account all the dominant kinetic effects along with the fast and slow gas heating. The model is developed on the basis of detailed kinetic PAC simulations, and the detailed mechanism previously validated in [20] which has been extended to burnt gases for the current study.

The proposed model mimics the plasma discharge effects on the reacting flow without describing the plasma itself, thus reducing significantly the computational cost of PAC simulations.

The paper proceeds as follows. The concepts of the newly proposed phenomenological model are first presented in Section 2. Then in Section 3, an analysis is performed to build the model parameters in air and methane-air mixtures, including both fresh and burnt gases. Finally in Section 4, the new model is validated with fully coupled detailed plasma-assisted ignition simulations. Comparison with the model from [26] is also provided and analysed.

2. Plasma-assisted combustion modelling

2.1. Phenomenological description of NRP discharges

The proposed model follows the same ideas of the phenomenological model presented in [26]. It intends to get rid of the time step Δt^p on the order of 1×10^{-12} s and the characteristic length Δx^p of a few micrometers required for detailed plasma simulations, both much smaller than typical scales used for combustion Large-Eddy Simulation (*i.e.* $\Delta t^{\text{LES}} = 10^{-9}$ to 10^{-6} s and $\Delta x^{\text{LES}} = 50 - 500 \mu\text{m}$). Moreover, fully coupled plasma-assisted combustion simulations usually require $N^* \gg 50$ species, and $P^* \gg 500$ reactions to describe the complex chemical interactions. In addition, modelling the discharge propagation involves solving new equations such as a drift-diffusion equation for each charged species self-coupled with a Poisson equation to get the electric field [24]. To overcome these constraints, the most important effects of NRP discharges on the gaseous mixture are incorporated into a phenomenological model, where the total discharge power \dot{E}^p is split into three components:

$$\dot{E}^p = \dot{E}_{\text{chem}}^p + \dot{E}_{\text{heat}}^p + \dot{E}_{\text{vib}}^p \quad (1)$$

where \dot{E}_{chem}^p represents the chemical effects, \dot{E}_{heat}^p the fast gas heating and \dot{E}_{vib}^p the non-equilibrium vibrational excitation that leads to a slow gas heating. More specifically, the proposed model is formulated to express the three different energy components via specific coefficients, corresponding to discharge energy fractions, α_j , α_{heat} and α_{vib} which must be determined, and that are defined as:

$$\dot{E}_{\text{chem}}^p = \sum_{j=1}^P \alpha_j \dot{E}^p = \alpha_{\text{chem}} \dot{E}^p, \quad \dot{E}_{\text{heat}}^p = \alpha_{\text{heat}} \dot{E}^p \quad \text{and} \quad \dot{E}_{\text{vib}}^p = \alpha_{\text{vib}} \dot{E}^p \quad (2)$$

where α_j is the discharge energy fraction associated to the process j and $\alpha_{\text{chem}} = \sum_j \alpha_j$ is the global chemical energy fraction resulting from P reactions involving N species both much lower than in the detailed kinetic simulations (N^* species and P^* reactions). In the present model, the fast and slow gas heating effects are modelled globally without detailed chemical description respectively in α_{heat} and α_{vib} . By construction these coefficients satisfy:

$$\sum_{j=1}^P \alpha_j + \alpha_{\text{heat}} + \alpha_{\text{vib}} = 1 \quad (3)$$

It is worth noting that this model ensures the energy conservation from the discharge to the gas and can be easily implemented in any Navier-Stokes based code, as detailed in Section 2.2.

The models coefficients, denoted α in general, depend on several variables such as the gaseous thermochemical state $\mathcal{S} = (Y_{k=1,\dots,N}, T, P)$ and the electric field E . Before going into the details, the overall methodology of the model is

depicted in Fig. 1. First, detailed kinetic simulations are conducted using isochoric plasma reactors as detailed in previous work of the authors [20]. These simulations describe the plasma chemical activity resulting from a single pulse at a given reduced electric field E/N and gaseous state \mathcal{S} . In these simulations, a detailed kinetic mechanism is used, including electron impact reactions, ion chemistry, vibrational and electronic excitation and relaxation. These simulations give access to the molar production rate $\dot{\omega}_k^{p,*}$ resulting from plasma processes, which can be used to determine how the discharge energy is split into the chemical, heat and vibration effects. The analysis of $\dot{\omega}_k^{p,*}$ provides an estimate of the discharge energy fractions α that are ultimately used in the flow equations, where only ground state neutral species are considered.

Figure 1: Overview of the methodology employed to determine the coefficients α_j , α_{heat} and α_{vib} in the PACMIND model: from 0D detailed kinetic simulations toward Large-Eddy Simulation of plasma-assisted combustion.

2.2. Governing equations

The chemical, heat and vibrational excitation effects, discussed in Section 2, are included in the compressible reactive Navier-Stokes equations, \dot{E}_{chem}^p being associated to the molecular production rate $\dot{\omega}_k^p$, complemented with a transport equation for the global non-equilibrium vibrational energy e_{vib} which then read:

$$\frac{\partial \rho Y_k}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho Y_k (\mathbf{u} + \mathbf{V}_k)) = W_k \dot{\omega}_k^c + W_k \dot{\omega}_k^p \quad (4)$$

$$\frac{\partial \rho \mathbf{u}}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho \mathbf{u} \mathbf{u} + p \mathbf{I}) = \nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\tau} \quad (5)$$

$$\frac{\partial \rho E_s}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot ((\rho E_s + p) \mathbf{u}) = \nabla \cdot (\boldsymbol{\tau} \cdot \mathbf{u} - \mathbf{q}) + \dot{\omega}_T^c + \dot{E}_{\text{heat}}^p + \dot{R}_{VT} \quad (6)$$

$$\frac{\partial \rho e_{\text{vib}}}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho e_{\text{vib}} \mathbf{u}) = \nabla \cdot (\rho \mathcal{D}_{\text{N}_2} \nabla e_{\text{vib}}) + \dot{E}_{\text{vib}}^p - \dot{R}_{VT} \quad (7)$$

where ρ is the mass density, \mathbf{u} the gaseous velocity, p the pressure, Y_k the mass fraction of species k , $\boldsymbol{\tau}$ the viscous stress tensor, \mathbf{q} the heat flux vector, \mathbf{V}_k the diffusion velocity of species k into the mixture, $\dot{\omega}_k^c$ and $\dot{\omega}_T^c$ the species k molar production rate and heat release rate due to non-plasma chemical processes, \mathcal{D}_{N_2} is the diffusion coefficient of N_2 into the mixture used for the vibrational energy, and E_s the total non-chemical energy defined by:

$$E_s = \frac{1}{2} \mathbf{u} \cdot \mathbf{u} + \sum_{k=1}^{N^{\text{NS}}} e_{sk} Y_k \quad (8)$$

where N^{NS} is the number of species in the mixture and e_{sk} the sensible energy of species k . Equations 4 to 7 are solved in the AVBP code [34], a well-established solver for combustion and aerodynamic applications.

The plasma effects are taken into account via $\dot{\omega}_k^p$, the species k molar production rate due to plasma chemical processes which is consistent with the chemical energy $\dot{E}_{\text{chem}}^p = \sum_k^N e_k \dot{\omega}_k^p$ with e_k the internal energy of species k , \dot{E}_{heat}^p the fast gas heating and the vibrational energy modelled by Eq. 7. At the end of the discharge, the total chemical energy is increased by the total discharge energy E^p while the total non-chemical energy increases by $E^p - E_{\text{chem}}^p$. Additionally, the non-equilibrium vibrational energy is treated separately whereas the equilibrium one is considered within the standard thermodynamic properties of

the mixture. Consequently, the non-equilibrium vibrational energy source term \dot{E}_{vib}^p must be removed from the mixture energy. At the end, using Eq. 1, only the fast gas heating term remains on the right hand side of the energy equation (Eq. 6). These plasma source terms (*i.e.*, $\dot{\omega}_k^p$, \dot{E}_{heat}^p and \dot{E}_{vib}^p) depend on the spatial coordinates \mathbf{x} reflecting the discharge position and shape, the time t , the thermo-chemical states \mathcal{S} and the electric field magnitude E . Equation 7 includes the vibrational energy power source term occurring during the discharge \dot{E}_{vib}^p and its relaxation to translational energy (*i.e.*, slow gas heating) via \dot{R}_{VT} which depends on the non-equilibrium vibrational energy e_{vib} and the thermo-chemical state \mathcal{S} . As these two phenomena do not occur at the same timescale, both convection and diffusion processes are considered in the transport equation. It is assumed that e_{vib} diffuses as N_2 which is the dominant vibrationally excited molecules in NRP discharges. More details concerning the vibrational energy treatment are given in Section 2.3.

2.3. Vibrational energy production and relaxation

The vibration of nitrogen plays an essential role in plasma-assisted combustion, even at high reduced electric fields, as it can store up to 50% of the discharge energy [1]. In Eq. 7, the vibrational energy source terms are divided into an ultra-fast production \dot{E}_{vib}^p and a slow relaxation \dot{R}_{VT} .

Regarding the fast vibrational energy excitation, a significant part is produced via electron impact excitation reactions of nitrogen vibrational modes summarised by Eq. 9. As shown in [35], a vibrational energy residual is also present during the quenching of an excited nitrogen molecule $\text{N}_2^{(*1)}$ into a lower level $\text{N}_2^{(*2)}$ as represented by Eq. 10. The two aforementioned processes are thus considered to estimate \dot{E}_{vib}^p .

The relaxation of vibrational energy to translational energy is dominated by the process given by Eq. 11 which slowly heats the gas. The rate of this process strongly depends on the colliding partner M for which N_2 , O_2 , CO_2 , H_2O , H_2 , OH , H and O have been considered in this work.

The relaxation term \dot{R}_{VT} , which controls the rate at which the vibration is converted to heat, is computed using the Landau-Teller harmonic oscillator assumption [36, 37]:

$$\dot{R}_{VT} = \rho \frac{e_{\text{vib}}}{\tau_{VT}} \quad (12)$$

$$\frac{1}{\tau_{VT}} = \sum_M \frac{1}{\tau_{VT}^M} \quad (13)$$

where the relaxation times τ_{VT}^M are computed using the coefficients from [1] for the processes given by Eq. 11 with all M except O , and from [38] for $M \equiv O$. The relaxation source term \dot{R}_{VT} appearing in Eq. 7 goes to gaseous mixture energy Eq. 6, resulting in the slow gas heating effect of the NRP discharges.

2.4. Plasma processes

In the model of [26], the discharge chemical energy only accounts for the ultra-fast dissociation of the oxygen molecule. The herein proposed model extends the chemical effects to $j \in [1, P]$ processes associated with N species,

allowing to model the wide variety of chemical reactions that occurs during the discharge. Each chemical process j is written as:

$$\sum_{k=1}^N \nu_{kj} \mathcal{M}_k = 0 \quad (14)$$

where \mathcal{M}_k symbolizes species k , $\nu_{kj} = \nu''_{kj} - \nu'_{kj}$ with ν'_{kj} and ν''_{kj} the molar stoichiometric coefficients of species k , as reactant or product respectively in reaction j . From the whole set of processes, the molar production rate $\dot{\omega}_k^p$ of a species k due to the plasma discharge reads:

$$\dot{\omega}_k^p = \sum_{j=1}^P \nu_{kj} \mathcal{Q}_j \quad (15)$$

where \mathcal{Q}_j is the net molar progress rate of the process j . Equation 15 can be written in the form of a linear system:

$$\mathbf{A} \mathbf{x} = \mathbf{b} \quad (16)$$

where $\mathbf{A} = (\nu_{ij})$ is the $N \times P$ stoichiometric coefficients matrix, $\mathbf{x} = (\mathcal{Q}_j)$ is the molar production rates vector of the P processes considered in the model and $\mathbf{b} = (\dot{\omega}_k^p)$ is the molar species production rate vector of size N due to the plasma discharge.

2.5. Energy distribution modelling

In the model formulation of Eq. 2, a first step is to determine the discharge power distribution $\dot{E}^p(x, y, z, t)$. This spatio-temporal energy deposition is characterized by its frequency f and pulse duration T_p to provide a total energy per pulse E^p , or equivalently an energy density $e^p = E^p/V_p$ in a zero-dimensional reactor with V_p a discharge volume. The discharge power \dot{E}^p is assumed to be temporally constant during the pulse. The pulse duration T_p of the model is

defined to include the high voltage pulse $t \in [0, t_{\text{off}}]$ during which the discharge energy e_{target}^p is deposited and the electronic states relaxation $t \in [t_{\text{off}}, t_{\text{end}}]$ as shown schematically in Fig. 2. The end of the pulse t_{off} is defined by the time at which $e^p = e_{\text{target}}^p$, whereas t_{off} is a compromise to include plasma energy relaxation to the gas without significant influence of neutral reactions. At the end of the pulse, the targeted discharge energy density has been deposited at a fixed effective reduced electric field E/N_{eff} .

Figure 2: Reduced electric field E/N used in the zero-dimensional reactors and the associated discharge energy density e^p trend resulting from the simulation.

The spatial profile is given by a density function $\mathcal{F}(x, y, z)$, satisfying Eq. 17 with V the discharge volume, which must approximate the discharge energy density on the considered configuration as it will be shown in Sections 3.1.2 and 4.3.1.

$$\int_V \mathcal{F} dV = 1 \quad (17)$$

Finally, the spatio-temporal discharge power reads:

$$\dot{E}^p(x, y, z, t) = \begin{cases} \frac{E^p}{T_p} \mathcal{F}(x, y, x) & \text{if } t' \in [0, T_p] \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (18)$$

where $t' = t \bmod (1/f)$ is defined as the time from the beginning of the current

pulse.

2.6. Model closure

To complete the model, the discharge energy fractions associated to the (i) fast kinetic effects α_j , (ii) fast gas heating α_{heat} and (iii) slow gas heating due vibrational energy relaxation α_{vib} , must be determined. To this end, detailed kinetic simulations are performed using the detailed plasma-combustion chemical mechanism developed in [39]. This mechanism has been extensively validated against experimental measurements of NRP discharges in air and methane-air mixtures, as detailed in [20], including various experimental measurements such as atomic oxygen production in air and methane-air [27, 33], fast gas heating [27, 40], vibrationally excited nitrogen population [40] and ignition delay time [41]. It has been extended in [42] to mixtures containing combustion products in order to model the discharges occurring in burnt gas regions, which is often the case in real burners, as in [43, 32]. The CANTERA [44] chemical solver coupled to BOLOS [45] is used here to perform the zero-dimensional simulations. More details about the chemical modelling can be found in [39]. In what follows, variables with superscript $*$ correspond to properties in the detailed simulations and must be differentiated from those in the model. As in Eq. 4, the overall mechanism is split in two sets of reactions, corresponding to the conventional combustion reactions \mathcal{C} (the reactions from the GRI 3.0 [46] in this work) and to the plasma reactions \mathcal{P} :

$$\dot{\omega}_k^* = \sum_{j \in \mathcal{P}} \dot{\omega}_{k,j}^* + \sum_{j \in \mathcal{C}} \dot{\omega}_{k,j}^* = \dot{\omega}_k^{C,*} + \dot{\omega}_k^{P,*} \quad (19)$$

where $\dot{\omega}_{k,j}^*$ is the molar production rate of species k in the reaction j .

Since the model aims to eliminate the plasma transient effects, only the

global plasma discharge effects are considered in the model. Thus, the mean molar species production rates are used in Eq. 16. To do so, $\dot{\omega}_k^{p,*}(t)$ is averaged over a single time-interval $[0, T_p]$ during which fast transient plasma effects occur:

$$\overline{\dot{\omega}_k^{p,*}} = \frac{1}{T_p} \int_0^{T_p} \dot{\omega}_k^{p,*} dt \quad (20)$$

As explained above, the plasma processes induce variations of the system energy, categorized in chemical and vibrational contributions. In the detailed kinetic description, additional contributions are added corresponding to electronic excitation and ionization. Note that these additional contributions are included for analysis but are ignored in the model as they quickly vanish. The various energy contributions may be expressed with the internal energy u_k of the k^{th} species, similarly split into four parts:

$$u_k = u_{k,\text{chem}} + u_{k,\text{vib}} + u_{k,\text{exc}} + u_{k,\text{ion}} \quad (21)$$

where $u_{k,\text{chem}}$ is the internal energy of the associated ground state species, $u_{k,\text{vib}}$ the vibrational energy, $u_{k,\text{exc}}$ the electronic excitation energy and $u_{k,\text{ion}}$ the ionization energy. In the detailed kinetic modelling, only the energy densities are considered as zero-dimensional reactors are used. The discharge energy density is divided in different channels e_{channel}^p for channel $\in \{\text{chem, vib, exc, ion}\}$ which are simply given by:

$$e_{\text{channel}}^p = \sum_{k=1}^{N^*} \int_t \dot{\omega}_k^{p,*} u_{k,\text{channel}} dt \quad (22)$$

where N^* is the number of species in the detailed mechanism. Finally, the discharge heating effect is computed using Eq. 23 where Δu_j is the reaction energy change per mole and Q_j^* the molar reaction rate of reaction j . For

heavy species reactions, the reaction energy change is classically defined by $\Delta u_j = \sum_k \nu_{kj} u_k$ while for electron impact reactions $\Delta u_j = (\sum_k \nu_{kj} u_k) - \epsilon_{\text{th}}^j$ with ϵ_{th}^j the energy threshold of reaction j which is lost by the electron.

$$e_{\text{heat}}^{\text{P}} = - \int_t \sum_{j \in \mathcal{P}} \mathcal{Q}_j^* \Delta u_j \, dt \quad (23)$$

The total plasma discharge energy density e^{P} is then the sum of all contributions:

$$e^{\text{P}} = e_{\text{chem}}^{\text{P}} + e_{\text{heat}}^{\text{P}} + e_{\text{vib}}^{\text{P}} + e_{\text{exc}}^{\text{P}} + e_{\text{ion}}^{\text{P}} \quad (24)$$

This total discharge energy density e^{P} is known from the discharge properties:

$$e^{\text{P}} = \int_t \mathbf{j}_{\text{e}} \cdot \mathbf{E} \, dt \quad (25)$$

where \mathbf{j}_{e} is the electron current density and \mathbf{E} is the electric field.

Finally, the discharge energy fractions used in the model can be determined from the 0D modelling using:

$$\alpha_{\text{chem}} = e_{\text{chem}}^{\text{P}}/e^{\text{P}} \quad \alpha_{\text{heat}} = (e_{\text{heat}}^{\text{P}} + e_{\text{ion}}^{\text{P}} + e_{\text{exc}}^{\text{P}})/e^{\text{P}} \quad \alpha_{\text{vib}} = e_{\text{vib}}^{\text{P}}/e^{\text{P}} \quad (26)$$

where the ionisation and excitation energy residuals at the end of detailed modelling are assumed to be responsible for fast gas heating. The individual plasma processes considered in the model still have to be estimated, which require the determination of α_j . In general, the number of processes P differs from the number of species N in the model so that the stoichiometric coefficients matrix \mathbf{A} in Eq. 16 has a rectangular shape. As a consequence, there is no unambiguous relation between the net molar progress rate \mathcal{Q}_j of the model and the molar

production rates $\dot{\omega}_k^{p,*}$ from the detailed simulation. In the procedure used to determine α_j , more emphasis is put on the radicals that are of interest. By doing so, the error made on the species that are produced by the discharge (*i.e.*, the species for which $\bar{\omega}_k^{p,*} \geq 0$) is minimized. First, \mathcal{Q}_j is determined using the averaged molar production rates from the detailed kinetic simulation (*i.e.*, $\overline{\dot{\omega}_k^{p,*}}$) using Eq. 16. Then, the energy fraction α_j is simply computed using:

$$\alpha_j = \frac{\mathcal{Q}_j T_p \Delta u_j}{e^p} \quad (27)$$

2.7. Objectives and limits of the model

This work aims to extend the phenomenological model proposed in [26] by focusing on the kinetic description of the model. This simplified model is intended to be used for the study of plasma-combustion interaction in complex flows and geometries where fully coupled detailed simulations would require a prohibitive computational cost. By construction, the model deliberately leaves out part of the phenomena resulting from the coupling between these two physics, for which more elaborate models or experiment still need to be developed. In particular, the description of the spatial density function \mathcal{F} in Eq. 18 is a difficult task. It depends on various factors, such as the electrode configuration and the electrical parameters [47, 22]. These uncertainties raise some difficulties when comparing with experiment, as the discharge radius may lead to very different post-discharge patterns such as cylindrical or toroidal kernel expansion [16]. Moreover, pulse-to-pulse coupling obtained at high frequency is difficult to reproduce with a simplified model such as the one developed in this work. It must be noted that the present model avoids describing the electric field inhomogeneity due to space charge and electrode curvature. In particular, the model does not account for sheath formation which causes spatial disturbance in the electrical potential due to charge accumulation. The sheath formation

requires streamer models including physical boundary conditions at the electrode surface to manage charged species fluxes [48, 49]. The electric field inhomogeneity induced by the electrode curvature could be estimated prior to the simulation by solving a Poisson equation to obtain the Laplacian electric field. As well, the presence of temperature gradients could be managed by computing the reduced electric field with the local gas density. Note also that the model needs to be supplemented by electrical characterisation of the discharge, including synchronised voltage and current measurements to estimate an effective reduced electric field and total deposited energy which can be achieved experimentally [50]. Discharge energy measurements can in turn be included in the model by adjusting e_{target}^p to the studied case. As the reduced electric field is of primary importance when considering NRP discharges, simplified estimate of it, as in this work, must be done cautiously and is a key issue for the future model improvements. The time evolution of the model energy deposition is oversimplified and does not consider in detail the different phases observed during the discharge and afterglow. Finally, a very difficult task is to incorporate gaseous composition variation in the model, which must be given as an input of the model prior to the simulation. At the end, the model presented in this work must be seen as a compromise between accuracy and complexity to model NRP discharges in real-size configurations, that must be fed by detailed modelling or experiment.

3. Results in various mixtures

The model presented in Section 2 is now applied to discharges in various mixtures. In Section 3.1, the model is applied to discharges in air and compared with results obtained with the model of [26] in a reference case. Then in Section 3.2, the model is extended to methane-air mixtures for various compo-

sitions and reduced electric fields.

3.1. NRP discharges in air

3.1.1. Chemical processes and model parameters

The most important processes in air are determined based on our previous work on detailed kinetic mechanism for plasma-assisted combustion [39]. The NRP discharge experiment in air from [27] has been simulated using a zero-dimensional reactor with Cantera [44]. In this experiment, a high voltage pulse corresponding to $E/N \simeq 150$ Td is applied and switched off at $t_{\text{off}} \simeq 25$ ns. The simulation yields very good agreement with the experiment concerning the fast gas heating, atomic oxygen production and electronically excited nitrogen molecules dynamics. With the help of these simulations, it is possible to determine how the discharge energy is distributed within the chemical, heat and vibrational energies as described in Section 2.6. This has been done during the high voltage pulse (*i.e.* $t \in [0-25]$ ns) and the following few tens of nanoseconds up to $t_{\text{end}} = 100$ ns to account for electronic energy relaxation. As shown in Fig. 3, the ionization energy is substantial only during the pulse and then quickly falls to zero. Vibrationally excited nitrogen molecules are efficiently produced during the pulse to represent approximately 20% of the discharge energy. The chemical energy is quickly stabilized after the pulse and reaches more than 40% of the discharge energy. Finally, the heating energy corresponds to 20% of the discharge energy at the end of the pulse, in agreement with experiment at the same time, and then continuously increases thanks to the electronic excitation energy relaxation. The higher value obtained in our simulation at $t = 100$ ns compared to the other works, $\alpha_{\text{heat}} \simeq 0.37$, is due this electronic energy relaxation.

Based on this detailed kinetic simulation, it appears that the most important

Figure 3: Discharge energy distribution: \blacktriangle $e_{\text{exc}}^{\text{P}}/e^{\text{P}}$, \bullet $e_{\text{vib}}^{\text{P}}/e^{\text{P}}$, \blacksquare $e_{\text{heat}}^{\text{P}}/e^{\text{P}}$, \blacklozenge $e_{\text{chem}}^{\text{P}}/e^{\text{P}}$, \star $e_{\text{ion}}^{\text{P}}/e^{\text{P}}$

species produced by the discharge are O, N and NO as shown in Fig. 4.

Figure 4: Density of the main species produced during the high voltage pulse in the conditions of [27].

The atomic oxygen production is largely dominated by the two following processes:

which can be summarised by a global process:

The nitrogen atoms N are primarily produced by electron impact dissociation (*i.e.* $e^- + \text{N}_2 \longrightarrow e^- + 2\text{N}$) which can be globally viewed as:

Finally, a non-negligible amount of nitric oxide is produced by the plasma discharge. This NO production can lead to the production of stable NOx at longer times which should be avoided in combustion applications due to its environmental impact. Thus, while its production represents less than 1% of the discharge energy, it is kept in the model to estimate the plasma NOx production. Thanks to a path flux analysis, it has been observed that the nitric oxide is mainly formed through the following two processes:

The last process is responsible for the production of atomic oxygen coming from the oxygen molecule dissociation already considered in the global process Eq. 30. Thus, the NO production can be summarised by:

The above mentioned global processes along with their respective internal energy changes are summarised in Tab. 1.

These processes form a chemical model composed of 3 reactions and 5 species

	Global process	Δu_j [kJ/mol]
Process 1	$\text{O}_2 \longrightarrow 2\text{O}$	498.3
Process 2	$\text{N}_2 \longrightarrow 2\text{N}$	945.4
Process 3	$\text{O}_2 + \text{N}_2 \longrightarrow 2\text{NO}$	182.5

Table 1: Description of the global processes in air considered in the phenomenological model. Δu_j corresponds to the internal energy change of the global process.

for which the linear system of Eq. 16 takes the form:

$$\underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} -1 & 0 & -1 \\ 0 & -1 & -1 \\ 2 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 2 \end{bmatrix}}_{\mathbf{A}} \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} \mathcal{Q}_1 \\ \mathcal{Q}_2 \\ \mathcal{Q}_3 \end{bmatrix}}_{\mathbf{x}} = \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} \dot{\omega}_{\text{O}_2} \\ \dot{\omega}_{\text{N}_2} \\ \dot{\omega}_{\text{O}} \\ \dot{\omega}_{\text{N}} \\ \dot{\omega}_{\text{NO}} \end{bmatrix}}_{\mathbf{b}} \quad (35)$$

By focusing on the three active species produced by the discharge (*i.e.*, O, N and NO), the associated sub-system (rows 3, 4 and 5 of the stoichiometric matrix \mathbf{A}) gives:

$$\mathcal{Q}_1 = \frac{\dot{\omega}_{\text{O}}}{2}, \quad \mathcal{Q}_2 = \frac{\dot{\omega}_{\text{N}}}{2}, \quad \mathcal{Q}_3 = \frac{\dot{\omega}_{\text{NO}}}{2} \quad (36)$$

which minimizes the error on the species produced by the discharge. Based on the detailed chemical simulation, the model parameters in the conditions of the experiment from [27] have been computed and are given in Tab. 2, together with values from the literature [27, 28, 26]. A very good agreement is found for the atomic oxygen production (process 1) compared to the literature in this case. The PACMIND model allows to go deeper into the chemical description with 5.2% and 0.45% of the discharge energy respectively devoted to the production of atomic nitrogen (process 2) and nitric oxide (process 3). The chemical energy of the PACMIND model has been compared to the total chemical energy change

in the reactor, allowing to define an error $\varepsilon_{\text{chem}}$ given by:

$$\varepsilon_{\text{chem}} = \frac{|e_{\text{chem}}^{\text{p,model}} - e_{\text{chem}}^{\text{p}}|}{e_{\text{chem}}^{\text{p}}} \quad (37)$$

where $e_{\text{chem}}^{\text{p,model}}$ is computed from the model parameters using Eq. 38 and $e_{\text{chem}}^{\text{p}}$ from the detailed simulation using Eq. 39.

	This work	[27]	[28]	[26]
α_{chem}	0.428	0.35	0.35	0.32
α_1	0.3715	0.35	0.35	0.32
α_2	0.052	-	-	-
α_3	0.0045	-	-	-
α_{heat}	0.369	0.20	0.25	0.23
α_{vib}	0.203	-	-	0.45

Table 2: Discharge energy repartition in the experimental conditions of [27] using the detailed chemical simulation from our previous work [39] compared to the experimental results of [27], the simulation of [28] and the model of [26].

$$e_{\text{chem}}^{\text{p,model}} = T_p \times \sum_{k=1}^N \dot{\omega}_k^p u_{k,\text{chem}} \quad (38)$$

$$e_{\text{chem}}^{\text{p}} = \sum_{k=1}^{N^*} \int_t \dot{\omega}_k^{p,*} u_{k,\text{chem}} dt \quad (39)$$

Less than 0.1% difference has been observed in the case considered, so that the global chemical processes identified in the PACMIND model are representative of the discharge chemical effect. Our estimate of the discharge energy fraction spent to heat the gas is noticeably higher than the values given in the literature [27]. This difference is mainly due to the fact that this value has been experimentally estimated directly at the end of the pulse. At the same time (*i.e.*, $t = 25$ ns), our detailed modeling predicts that 21% of the discharge energy is converted to heat, and more than 15% of the discharge energy is still stored in electronic excitation as shown in Fig. 3. A large part of this electronic excitation is then relaxed to heat the gas, without any significant kinetic effect

or vibrational excitation. At $t = 100$ ns, it has been assumed that the remaining electronic excitation corresponds to heat. Finally, our simulation provides an estimate of the vibrational excitation energy with $\alpha_{\text{vib}} \simeq 0.2$. As expected, the overall results of the PACMIND model are in good agreements with the baseline Castela model which has been developed on this specific case.

3.1.2. 2D simulation of a single pulse in air

This case serves as a validation for our model by comparison with experimental measurements from [27] and simulation from [26]. The pin-pin configuration was studied in [27] and is depicted in Fig. 5a. The 2D simulation corresponds to the transverse plane (x, y) at the center of the 4 mm inter-electrode gap as shown in Fig. 5b. The initial conditions are taken from the experimental measurements: $P_0 = 1$ atm, $T_0 = 1500$ K and $\text{O}_2:\text{N}_2:\text{O} = 18.6:77.3:4.1$ (in mole) corresponding to an atomic oxygen density $n_{\text{O}} = 2 \times 10^{17} \text{ cm}^{-3}$. A single pulse is applied in the steady state regime (*i.e.*, no difference from pulse to pulse), with an energy $E^p = 670 \mu\text{J}$ and a discharge radius $r_0 = 225 \mu\text{m}$. To mimic this energy deposition, the discharge duration is set to $T_p = 50$ ns as in [26] and a sigmoid shape density function is used:

$$\mathcal{F}(r) = \frac{1}{\pi r_0^2 L_d} \frac{1}{1 + \exp((r - r_0)/\sigma_0)} \quad (40)$$

where $r = \sqrt{x^2 + y^2}$ is the distance from the discharge axis, L_d is the inter-electrode distance, r_0 represents the discharge channel radius and σ_0 is a characteristic size for the spatial profile transition as depicted in Fig. 5c. In our simulation, a short transition $\sigma_0 = 25 \mu\text{s}$ has been used to model the sharp discharge layer.

Two simulations have been performed with AVBP: one considering the orig-

Figure 5: Sketch of the experimental setup and the transverse considered plane (a), two-dimensional domain used in the simulation (b) and sigmoid shape density function \mathcal{F} (c).

inal Castela model from [26] and another one considering the parameters estimated in this work for the PACMIND model. The air sub-mechanism of the GRI 3.0 mechanism [46] has been considered.

The temporal evolutions of the atomic oxygen density and the gas temperature at the center of the discharge are shown in Fig. 6. In addition to the two simulations, the experimental measurements from [27] are also given. Figure 6a shows that the AVBP results with the Castela model slightly underestimate the atomic oxygen production (*i.e.*, $\Delta n_{\text{O}} \simeq \max(n_{\text{O}}) - n_{\text{O}}(t = 0) = 0.6 \times 10^{24} \text{ m}^{-3}$) compared with the experimental results ($\Delta n_{\text{O}}^{\text{exp}} \simeq 0.9 \times 10^{24} \text{ m}^{-3}$). The simulation with the PACMIND model developed in this work gives satisfying results compared with the experiment. Concerning the gas temperature (Fig. 6b), the AVBP simulation with the Castela model leads to an increase of 1200 K at the end of the discharge energy deposition. The PACMIND model leads to a higher gas temperature at the end of the pulse, which is in qualitative agreement with the experimental measurement at $t = 270 \text{ ns}$. Indeed, the first temperature mea-

surement during the pulse reflection (\star) is not affected by the reflection but only by the main pulse. Thus, it allows to estimate the effects of the excitation energy relaxation and pressure wave expansion during the 250 ns following the pulse. From this information, the gas temperature between 20 and 270 ns must reach values above 2900 K as is the case with the PACMIND model.

Figure 6: Results of NRP discharges in air representative of the experiment from [27]: (\bullet) main experimental pulse [27], (\blacktriangle) pulse reflection [27], (\star) measurements before plasma effect, ($—$) AVBP Castela and ($- - -$) AVBP PACMIND.

3.2. NRP discharges in methane-air mixtures

The PACMIND model in air is now extended to methane-air mixtures, including both fresh and burnt gases compositions, in order to simulate reactive cases. The analysis is performed using zero-dimensional reactors for which the numerical setup is presented in Section 3.2.1. From these simulations, the main plasma processes are identified in Section 3.2.2. Finally, the model parameters are presented in Section 3.2.3.

3.2.1. Numerical setup

The discharge effects are analyzed using 0D isochoric plasma reactors in Cantera [39]. A step pulse with an effective reduced electric field $E/N_{\text{eff}} = 200$ Td is applied as shown in Fig. 2. The pulse duration t_{off} is automatically adjusted

to deposit a targeted energy density e_{target}^p which has been set to $0.1 \text{ J} \cdot \text{cm}^{-3}$. Then, the simulation is continued up to $t_{\text{end}} = 100 \text{ ns}$ in order to relax the electronic excitation energy into other energy channels.

Two cases are considered to analyze the effects of the discharges in a reactive methane-air mixture. The corresponding initial conditions are given in Tab. 3. The first case, called FG, corresponds to the fresh gases composition of a lean methane-air 1D flame at $\phi = 0.8$, $T_0 = 300 \text{ K}$, and $P_0 = 1 \text{ atm}$. The second case, called BG, corresponds to the burnt gases composition of the previously described 1D flame which has been computed with Cantera.

	FG	BG
X_{O_2}	0.194	0.039
X_{N_2}	0.729	0.728
X_{CH_4}	0.077	-
X_{CO_2}	-	0.077
$X_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$	-	0.154
X_{OH}	-	1.7×10^{-3}
X_{CO}	-	5.5×10^{-4}
X_{H_2}	-	2.4×10^{-4}
X_{O}	-	1.4×10^{-4}
X_{H}	-	2.7×10^{-5}
X_{NO}	-	2.1×10^{-5}
$T \text{ [K]}$	300	2000

Table 3: Mixture composition and temperature of the two cases considered and corresponding to fresh gases (FG) and burnt gases (BG) of a one-dimensional flame at $\phi = 0.8$, $T_0 = 300 \text{ K}$, and $P_0 = 1 \text{ atm}$ computed with Cantera and the GRI-3.0 mechanism [46].

3.2.2. Additional processes

The simulations in fresh and burnt gases permit to identify new key species produced by the discharge. In addition to species already identified in air (O, N and NO), four species are significantly produced in the FG and BG cases: CH_3 , H, OH and CO as shown in Fig. 7.

Based on a path-flux analysis in the FG case, a very large part of the CH_3 and H plasma production is due to the following processes:

Figure 7: Density of the main species produced during a single pulse in (a) fresh gases and (b) burnt gases of a lean ($\phi = 0.8$) methane-air mixture.

which can be summarised by a global process:

The plasma discharge is also able to enhance the methane oxidation by producing a significant amount of excited atomic oxygen $\text{O}(^1\text{D})$ which can overcome the energy barrier of the conventional methane oxidation $\text{CH}_4 + \text{O} \longrightarrow \text{CH}_3 + \text{OH}$. The excited atomic oxygen $\text{O}(^1\text{D})$ reacts with CH_4 in a barrier-less reaction $\text{CH}_4 + \text{O}(^1\text{D}) \longrightarrow \text{CH}_3 + \text{OH}$ occurring at a high rate $k = 1.89 \times 10^{-10} \text{ cm}^3 \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$. As $\text{O}(^1\text{D})$ is coming from O_2 plasma dissociation, the methane oxidation by excited atomic oxygen is represented by the following global process:

Notice that in Fig. 7a, the CO production is induced by conventional combustion reactions dominated by $\text{CH}_3 + \text{O} \longrightarrow \text{CO} + \text{H}_2 + \text{H}$. On the contrary in burnt gases (see Figure 7b), a significant part of the CO production is generated by:

which can be represented with the global process:

The plasma discharge is also able to dissociate a significant part of the water vapour in burnt gas conditions, either by electron impact dissociation Eq. 48 or dissociative quenching of electronically excited nitrogen Eq. 49, leading to the formation of OH and H radicals.

A global dissociation process dominates the plasma kinetic effect on H_2O :

To summarise, the global processes in air given in Tab. 1 must be completed by four additional processes, detailed in Tab. 4, to fully describe the kinetics of non-equilibrium plasma discharge in reactive CH_4 -air mixtures. In the end,

the PACMIND model for methane-air mixtures is made of 7 processes and 12 species.

	Global process	Δu_j [kJ/mol]
Process 4	$\text{CH}_4 \longrightarrow \text{CH}_3 + \text{H}$	439.5
Process 5	$\text{CO}_2 \longrightarrow \text{CO} + \text{O}$	532.1
Process 6	$\text{H}_2\text{O} \longrightarrow \text{OH} + \text{H}$	499.2
Process 7	$\text{CH}_4 + 0.5 \text{O}_2 \longrightarrow \text{CH}_3 + \text{OH}$	257.5

Table 4: Additional processes in CH_4 -air mixtures which must be added to the air processes in the phenomenological model. Δu_j corresponds to the internal energy change of the global process.

3.2.3. Model parameters

Similarly to the case in air from Section 3.1.1, the discharge energy has been split into the five energy channels presented in Section 2.6. Notice that there are significant uncertainties for H_2O dissociation and gas heating in burnt gases. The Triniti cross-sections [51] have been used for H_2O as they form a complete and consistent dataset that can be used within an EEDF (Electron Energy Distribution Function) solver such as BOLSIG+ [45]. In this dataset, a single electron impact dissociation process is given and the corresponding cross-section is shown in Fig. 8. This cross-section differs significantly from the recommended dissociation cross-section in [52], used for instance in [53], as shown in Fig. 8. To estimate the influence of the cross-section uncertainty, the Triniti dissociation cross-section has been split into two parts: part 1 corresponds to the Itikawa dissociation cross-section [52], and part 2 corresponds to the difference between the two cross-sections. Then, two cases can be considered: case BG1 considering part 1 as dissociation and part 2 as heat (*i.e.*, assuming that the electronic state produced is instantaneously quenched releasing heat) and case BG2 considering parts 1 and 2 as dissociation.

The energy fraction for the FG and BG cases are shown in Fig. 9. First of all, it is remarkable that the fractions of chemical, heat and vibrational energies in the FG and BG cases are very similar to those obtained in air. To compute

Figure 8: Electron impact cross-section of H_2O dissociation ($e^- + \text{H}_2\text{O} \longrightarrow e^- + \text{OH} + \text{H}$) from the Trinit database [51] and Itikawa compilation [52]. Zones 1 and 2 correspond to the Trinit cross-section splitting.

the contribution of each process in the model, the species produced by the discharge (*i.e.*, O, N, NO, CH_3 , H, CO and OH) have been used to compute the molar production rates of the model processes. This choice allows to minimize the error on the active species plasma production. In the FG case, the presence of methane reduces the O_2 and N_2 dissociation. However, the proportion of chemical energy remains close to the air case due to the methane dissociation and methane oxidation processes which use more than 10% of the discharge energy. For the discharge in lean burnt gases (BG cases), there is still 7% and 5% of the discharge energy which is respectively spent to dissociate O_2 (α_1) and N_2 (α_2). Due to the lower O_2 concentration, the NO production is significantly reduced in burnt gases compared to the discharge in fresh gases. About 5% of the discharge energy serves to dissociate CO_2 (α_5). Finally, the most significant chemical effect is the H_2O dissociation which takes approximately 25% of the discharge energy (BG1 case). In the BG2 case, there is an increase of 6% of the water dissociation along with a decrease of the heat released by the same proportion. In both cases, electron-impact dissociation of H_2O molecules corresponds to approximately half of the H_2O dissociation. Further studies in burnt gases condition must evaluate which option is the most realistic. As the model parameters do not change fundamentally between the two cases, the BG1 case

hypothesis is used in the rest of this work. In addition to the kinetic effects, the discharge spent more than 40% (BG1 case) of its energy to heat the gas. A summary of the model parameters in both conditions is given in Tab. 5.

Figure 9: Discharge energy distribution of a single pulse in (a) fresh gases and (b) burnt gases of a lean ($\phi = 0.8$) methane-air mixture: \blacktriangle e_{exc}^p/e^p , \bullet e_{vib}^p/e^p , \blacksquare e_{heat}^p/e^p , \blacklozenge e_{chem}^p/e^p , \star e_{ion}^p/e^p

	Air	FG	BG	
			BG1	BG2
α_{chem}	0.4275	0.455	0.417	0.477
α_1	0.371	0.31	0.07	
α_2	0.052	0.029	0.048	
α_3	0.0045	0.0055	9.5×10^{-4}	
α_4	0	0.098	0	
α_5	0	0	0.056	
α_6	0	0	0.24	0.3
α_7	0	0.013	0	
α_{heat}	0.369	0.345	0.41	0.35
α_{vib}	0.203	0.2	0.173	

Table 5: Phenomenological model parameters in the FG and BG cases. BG1 and BG2 cases correspond to different hypothesis on the electron impact dissociation of H_2O (see text). The results in air corresponds to the results of Section 3.1.1 which are recalled here for convenience. The processes related to the α_j can be found in Tabs. 1 and 4.

The model parameters mainly depend on the mixture composition characterised by the molar fractions $X_{k \in [1, N^*]}$ and the gas temperature T_g . In the case of a 1D laminar premixed flame, it is possible to map all the accessed physical regions with only one variable c , called progress variable, which varies from 0

in the fresh gases to 1 in the burnt gases. In this work, we defined this progress variable as:

$$c = \frac{Y_{\text{CO}} + Y_{\text{CO}_2}}{Y_{\text{CO}}^b + Y_{\text{CO}_2}^b} \quad (51)$$

where the superscript b stands for values in burnt gases. The model parameters across the 1D laminar premixed methane-air flame at $\phi = 0.8$, $T_0 = 300$ K and $P_0 = 1$ atm are shown in Fig 10. Eleven samples points i have been used as initial compositions and temperature of a 0D plasma reactor corresponding to the progress variable $c_i = i/10$, $i \in 0, 10$. A single pulse is then applied on each reactor at a constant reduced electric field of 200 Td that is representative of NRP discharge applications as previously described in Fig. 2. The discharge energy density is fixed to $e_0^p = 1 \times 10^5 \text{ J} \cdot \text{m}^{-3}$.

The discharge energy transferred to the chemical energy (α_{chem}) stays almost constant along the flame, starting from 45% in the fresh gases to 40% in the burnt gases. However, the processes responsible for the chemical effects vary drastically. In the details, the significant decrease of the atomic oxygen (α_1) and methane (α_4) dissociation are almost compensated by the water vapour (α_6) and carbon dioxide (α_5) dissociation. While not representing a significant part of the discharge energy, it is interesting to notice an appreciable reduction of NO production (α_3) for the discharge in burnt gases ($c = 1$) compared with to the fresh gases case ($c = 0$). The vibrational energy fraction is almost constant in all the cases corresponding to $\approx 20\%$ of the discharge energy. Thus, the chemical energy decrease is mainly balanced by an increase of the fast gas heating which passes from 35% to 42% from $c = 0$ to 1.

Figure 10: Model parameters variation along a 1D laminar premixed methane-air flame at $\phi = 0.8$, $T_0 = 300$ K and $P_0 = 1$ atm: (—) α_{chem} , (---) α_{heat} , (-·-·) α_{vib} , ● α_1 , ■ α_2 , ◆ α_3 , ★ α_4 , ▲ α_5 , ▼ α_6 and ► α_7 .

3.2.4. Effect of the reduced electric field

It is well known that the reduced electric field E/N is one of the most important parameter influencing the discharge effects on the mixture. To analyse its influence, the model parameters have been computed in both the fresh and burnt gases of the lean methane-air mixture ($\phi = 0.8$, $T_0 = 300$ K, $P_0 = 1$ atm) by varying $E/N \in [50, 300]$ with steps of 10 Td. Whereas the discharge can be self-sustained above the breakdown electric field E_b , this is not the case for $E \leq E_b$ due to electron attachment. In practice, discharges can be produced with a Laplacian electric field $E_0 = V/d$ lower than E_b , for example in a pin-pin configuration, due to a local electric field enhancement as for example in [54]. In that case, the ionization processes occur during the streamer head crossing in which the reduced electric field is extremely high ($E/N|_{\text{max}} = 600 - 1000$ Td). Then, the discharge energy is effectively deposited at an effective reduced electric field $E/N|_{\text{eff}}$ close to E_0 . This is modelled in a 0D reactor by using a double stage pulse as depicted in Fig. 11. In that case, a small fraction β of the discharge energy is deposited at a high reduced electric field $E/N|_{\text{max}}$ and the remaining energy is deposited at an effective reduced electric field $E/N|_{\text{eff}}$. This double stage

pulse has been used for the low reduced electric field cases ($E/N \in [50, 150]$ Td) with β defined in Tab. 6, $E/N|_{\max} = 800$ Td and $E/N|_{\text{eff}} = E/N$. These values have been chosen to deposit the targeted energy in less than 100 ns, without having a significant contribution of the high reduced electric field in the energy balance. For the cases above 150 Td ($\beta = 0$), the pulse detailed in Fig. 2 is used.

Figure 11: Double stage reduced electric field E/N used in the zero-dimensional reactors for low electric field discharge and the associated discharge energy density e^p trend.

E/N [Td]	50	60	70	80	90	[100-140]	>140
β	0.1	0.09	0.08	0.07	0.06	0.05	0

Table 6: Fraction β of the discharge energy is deposited at a high reduced electric field in the double pulse cases.

The reduced electric field influence on the model parameters is shown in Fig. 12. In both fresh and burnt gases, the vibrational excitation decreases significantly with the reduced electric field and dominates up to $E/N \simeq 120$ Td. The decrease of α_{vib} is accompanied by an increase of both α_{chem} and α_{heat} in the whole range of E/N except at very low values of E/N in burnt gases where the water vapour rotational excitation starts to play an important role. Indeed, in the model it has been assumed that all the rotational excitation relaxes instantaneously and heats the gas due to the fast rotational to translational relaxation time τ_{RT} on the order of 10^{-9} s for $\text{N}_2\text{-N}_2$ [27, 36]. In fresh gases, the chemical

energy channel α_{chem} is significant for $E/N \geq 120$ Td with more than 35% of the discharge and up to 48% at $E/N = 300$ Td. For $E/N \in [120 - 300]$ Td, the gas heating also plays a crucial role with approximately 35% of the discharge energy. A large part of the chemical energy is due to the O_2 dissociation which reaches $\alpha_1 \simeq 31\%$ at $E/N = 200$ Td. Increasing E/N also increases methane dissociation α_4 and methane oxidation α_7 . The NO production α_3 follows the trend of the nitrogen molecule dissociation α_2 which mainly increases with E/N . Indeed, the N atom production goes along with N^* production from which NO originates. In burnt gases, a similar energy is spent on the chemical and heat effects from 120 Td ($\simeq 35\%$) to 300 Td ($\simeq 45\%$). In that case, the water vapour dissociation is the dominant kinetic effect peaking at 300 Td with $\alpha_6 = 25\%$. A similar discharge energy fraction goes to the O_2 and CO_2 dissociation with a maximum close to 5%. The energy spent to N_2 is higher than in the fresh gases with $\alpha_2 \simeq 10\%$ at 300 Td. Interestingly, this increase of α_2 is accompanied by a significant decrease of the NO production compared to the fresh gases case by a factor five.

Figure 12: Influence of the reduced electric field E/N on the model parameters in (a) fresh gases and (b) burnt gases of a methane-air mixture at $\phi = 0.8$: (—) α_{chem} , (---) α_{heat} , (-·-·) α_{vib} , \bullet α_1 , \blacksquare α_2 , \blacklozenge α_3 , \star α_4 , \blacktriangle α_5 , \blacktriangledown α_6 and \blacktriangleright α_7 .

3.2.5. Effects of reduced electric field variations across a flame front

When discharges occur in a region crossed by a flame, the density variations from fresh to burnt gases result in significant changes of the reduced electric field E/N . This effect has been evaluated on a 1D laminar flame at $\phi = 0.8$, $T_0 = 300$ K and $P_0 = 1$ atm for which gas temperatures are given at different values of the progress variable c in Tab. 7. The applied electric field of $1.25 \times 10^6 \text{ V} \cdot \text{m}^{-1}$ corresponds for instance to an applied voltage of 10 kV and a gap distance of 8 mm, close to what is considered in [54]. The corresponding reduced electric field can be found in Tab. 7: it ranges from 50 to 340 Td respectively in fresh and burnt gases. The double-stage reactor presented in Fig. 11 is considered with non-zero β for the lowest reduced electric fields (see Tab. 7). The resulting model coefficients are shown in Fig. 13. The low reduced electric field in the fresh gases mainly leads to vibrational excitation, meaning that in this case the plasma effect is mostly restricted to slow gas heating. Then as the temperature rises, the fast chemical and heat effects become increasingly important to dominate over vibration for $c \geq 0.4$. For $c \geq 0.4$, chemical and heat effects slowly increase, varying from 30 to 40% of the discharge energy. However, the chemical processes in place vary a lot: O_2 and CH_4 dissociation being progressively replaced by CO_2 and H_2O dissociation when moving to burnt gases.

c	0	0.1	0.2	0.3	0.4	0.5	0.6	0.7	0.8	0.9	1.0
T [K]	300	606	823	1008	1172	1318	1448	1565	1667	1760	2001
E/N [Td]	51	103	140	172	199	224	246	266	284	299	340
β	0.1	0.05	0.05	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Table 7: Gas temperature, reduced electric field and β coefficient used for the study along a 1D laminar premixed methane-air flame at $\phi = 0.8$, $T_0 = 300$ K, $P_0 = 1$ atm and constant electric field $E = 1.25 \times 10^6 \text{ V} \cdot \text{m}^{-1}$.

3.2.6. Effects of the equivalence ratio

The influence of the equivalence ratio has been studied by varying $\phi \in [0.6, 1.0]$ in both fresh and burnt gases at $E/N = 200$ Td and the resulting

Figure 13: Model parameters variation along a 1D laminar premixed methane-air flame at $\phi = 0.8$, $T_0 = 300\text{ K}$, $P_0 = 1\text{ atm}$ and constant electric field $E = 1.25 \times 10^6\text{ V} \cdot \text{m}^{-1}$: (—) α_{chem} , (---) α_{heat} , (-·-·) α_{vib} , (●) α_1 , (■) α_2 , (◆) α_3 , (★) α_4 , (▲) α_5 , (▼) α_6 and (►) α_7 .

model parameters are shown in Fig. 14. In fresh gases (see Fig. 14a), the discharge energy fractions spent on the chemical, heat and vibrational energy are almost constant within the whole range of equivalence ratios considered. Regarding the kinetic effects, the decrease of oxygen molecule dissociation (α_1) when ϕ increases is balanced by an increase in both methane dissociation (α_4) and oxidation (α_7), as the methane molar fraction rises. In burnt gases (see Fig. 14b), a slight variation of the chemical and heat effects is observed. At $\phi = 0.6$, the kinetic effects dominate over the heat and vibrational effects with a large part of the energy spent in the O_2 (α_1) and H_2O (α_6) dissociation. Then, as the equivalence ratio increases, the O_2 dissociation rapidly decreases to reach negligible values at the stoichiometry where O_2 is fully consumed. This decrease is partially balanced by the increasing part of the energy going to H_2O , CO_2 and N_2 dissociation. However, the overall chemical effect declines and the gas heating becomes the dominant energy channel for $\phi \geq 0.7$. The vibrational excitation remains constant over the entire equivalence ratio range and takes approximately 18% of the discharge energy.

Figure 14: Influence of the equivalence ratio ϕ on the model parameters in (a) fresh gases and (b) burnt gases: (—) α_{chem} , (---) α_{heat} , (-·-·) α_{vib} , ● α_1 , ■ α_2 , ◆ α_3 , ★ α_4 , ▲ α_5 , ▼ α_6 and ► α_7 .

4. Plasma-assisted ignition

The model validation is finally performed by comparison with detailed coupled plasma-assisted combustion simulations. The comparison methodology is first presented in Section 4.1. Then, the results of the detailed simulations are given in Section 4.2. Finally in Section 4.3, the model developed in this work is compared with the model of [26] and the detailed simulations.

4.1. Numerical setup of the detailed simulations

To validate the phenomenological model, comparisons with detailed plasma-assisted ignition simulations are performed. These detailed simulations are performed with the AVBP-PAC solver presented in [24] where a low-temperature plasma solver [55] has been coupled with the reactive compressible Navier-Stokes solver AVBP [34]. In these detailed simulations, each charged species k is solved using a reactive drift-diffusion equation:

$$\frac{\partial \rho_k}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho_k \mu_k \mathbf{E} - D_k \nabla \rho_k) = \dot{\omega}_k \quad (52)$$

where ρ_k is the mass density, μ_k the mobility, D_k the diffusion coefficient and $\dot{\omega}_k$ the chemical source term. The charged species are coupled together self-consistently through the electric field \mathbf{E} which is derived from the Poisson equation:

$$\nabla^2 V = -\frac{1}{\epsilon_0} \sum_k q_k n_k \quad \text{with} \quad \mathbf{E} = -\nabla V \quad (53)$$

where V is the electric potential and q_k is the species k charge.

A pin-pin electrode configuration is used as in [24] with a 4 mm electrode gap distance and an electrode curvature radius of 200 μm (see Fig. 15). A single-pulse discharge is applied in a methane-air mixture initially at 500 K and 1 atm, and at various equivalence ratios $\phi \in [0.6 - 1]$. The applied voltage profile is shown in Fig. 16 where an initial rise of 1 ns is followed by a constant voltage plateau. The pulse amplitude has been varied from 8.2 kV to 14.7 kV, corresponding to a mean reduced electric field $E/N \in [150 - 250]$ Td in the electrode gap at the initial temperature. For all the cases, an initial ionization level of $1 \times 10^{15} \text{ m}^{-3}$ is used to mimic the photoionization effect as in [56]. The mobility and diffusion coefficients of the positive and negative ions are taken from [57] while all the electron related swarm parameters are computed using BOLSIG+ [45]. The different cases considered in this work are summarised in Tab. 8, sweeping both E/N and ϕ ranges.

		E/N [Td]		
		150	200	250
ϕ	0.6	EN150_φ06	EN200_φ06	EN250_φ06
	0.8	EN150_φ08	EN200_φ08	EN250_φ08
	1.0	EN150_φ10	EN200_φ10	EN250_φ10

Table 8: Summary of the cases considered for plasma-assisted ignition. All the cases are performed with a uniform initial temperature $T_0 = 500$ K and at atmospheric pressure.

The time evolution of the discharge energy E^p and energy density e^p are

defined in the detailed simulation by:

$$E^P(t) = \int_{V_p} e^P(t) dV \quad \text{and} \quad e^P(t) = \int_0^t \mathbf{j}_e \cdot \mathbf{E} dt \quad (54)$$

where \mathbf{j}_e is the electron current density and V_p the discharge volume. In order to control the discharge energy deposition, the voltage is switched off at t_{off} when the discharge energy E^P reaches a targeted value E_d , which has been set to $E_d = 750 \mu\text{J}$. This value ensures the mixture ignition using a single pulse in all the cases presented in Tab. 8.

Figure 15: Sketch of the geometry with mesh sizes and probes.

Figure 16: Temporal evolution of the discharge energy.

During the high voltage pulse, a fine triangular unstructured mesh is employed with a cell size $\Delta x_{\text{fine}} = 3 \mu\text{m}$ in the inter-electrode region (see Fig. 15) whereas the cell size is increased to $15 \mu\text{m}$ in this region during the inter-pulse. Outside of the discharge region, corresponding to Δx_{medium} in Fig. 15, the cell

sizes are $10\ \mu\text{m}$ and $30\ \mu\text{m}$ respectively during the pulse and the inter-pulse. Then in the far-field region, Δx_{coarse} is progressively increased to $250\ \mu\text{m}$ in both discharge phases. With this mesh, the flame front is resolved over at least 15 points. The boundary conditions for the Navier-Stokes equations, the charge species drift-diffusion equations and the Poisson equation for the electric field are given in Tab. 9.

	Anode	Cathode	Axis	Farfield
Navier-Stokes	Adiabatic non-slipping wall		Symmetry	Outlet NSCBC [58]
Drift-diffusion	Neumann		Symmetry	Outlet
Poisson	$V_a(t) \geq 0$	$V_c = 0$	Neumann	Neumann

Table 9: Boundary conditions used for the gaseous Navier-Stokes equations, the charged species drift-diffusion equations, and the Poisson equation for the electric field.

In a previous work [20], a detailed chemical mechanism has been developed for plasma-assisted combustion of CH_4 -air mixtures and reduced using the AR-CANE library [59]. The reduced mechanism is made of 44 species and 410 reactions. Besides being valid for plasma discharge cases, the reduced mechanism is also able to reproduce correctly conventional auto-ignition delay times of methane-air mixtures in a large range of temperatures [800 – 2000] K and equivalence ratios [0.5-1.5] as well as laminar flame speeds in a large range of equivalence ratios [0.6-1.4].

4.2. Results of the detailed simulations

The EN200_φ08 case (*i.e.*, $E/N = 200\ \text{Td}$, $\phi = 0.8$) is first considered to introduce the main phases of the plasma-assisted ignition. During the high voltage pulse, two streamers that originate from both electrode tips are moving at an extremely high velocity of around $1\ \text{mm} \cdot \text{ns}^{-1}$ as shown in Figs. 17a and 17c. Then, the positive and negative streamers merge to form a conductive channel as shown in Fig. 17b. Most of the discharge energy is deposited after the discharge channel is established. During this phase, the reduced electric field along

the axis is quasi-homogeneous at a value close to the Laplacian reduced electric field $E/N = V/(dN) = 200$ Td, without considering sheath formation due to the use of simplified electrode boundary conditions, as shown in Fig. 17d. In addition, the electrical current quickly rises at the end of the pulse. To avoid unacceptable current and perform comparison with experiment, an electrical circuit model could be introduced as in [60, 18]. However, the current peak of 80 A reached in this simulation remains acceptable regarding what a real power supply can achieve.

Figure 17: Discharge propagation (a,c) and discharge channel establishment (b,d) during the high voltage pulse of the EN200- ϕ 08 case.

During the high voltage pulse, the highly energetic electrons are able to produce a significant amount of excited molecules N_2^* , O^* as shown in Fig. 18a. Most of the electronically excited species are quickly quenched at the end of the pulse while a quick rise of some radicals can be observed in Fig. 18b. In addition to this chemical effect, the discharge is responsible for an ultra fast gas heating as shown in Fig. 19a where the gap temperature rises up to 3000 K close to the electrode tips. Following the pulse, the gap temperature still increases in an isochoric way due to the fast electronic energy relaxation as shown in Fig. 19b.

Then in the microsecond timescale, the hydrodynamic effects already observed in [24] start to play a crucial role as shown in Fig. 19c. After 100 μs , the two hot kernels initially formed at the electrode tips are convected toward the center of the gap and are fully detached from the electrode due to fresh gas entrance. In the conditions studied, the two kernels are able to grow and merge together at $t \simeq 250 \mu\text{s}$ (see Fig. 19e) to form a self-sustained cylindrical flame as shown in Fig. 19f.

Figure 18: Species production during the first instants of the EN200_ ϕ 08 case in the middle of the inter-electrode gap (probe 1 in Fig. 15): (a) electrons and electronically excited species and (b) main radicals produced by the discharge.

In all the plasma-assisted ignition cases studied in this section (see Tab. 8), the ignition sequences are similar to the one presented above for the EN200_ ϕ 08 case but with different ignition delay times. The ignition delay time τ_{ig} has been computed for all cases at a probe 2 located at $(x, r) = (0, 1)$ mm by Eq. (55) where $\Delta T = 1000 \text{ K}$ and $T_0 = 500 \text{ K}$ is the initial temperature.

$$\tau_{\text{ig}} = \min(t \mid T(t) \geq T_0 + \Delta T) \quad (55)$$

For all the equivalence ratios considered, an increase of the ignition delay time with the applied reduced electric field is observed within the interval $E/N \in [150, 250] \text{ Td}$ (see Tab. 10). In a previous study [20], a non-monotonic

Figure 19: Temperature maps of the different stages of the EN200_φ08 case ignition of the fully coupled simulation.

behaviour of the ignition delay time of a lean methane-air mixture versus the reduced electric field has been observed for zero-dimensional plasma-assisted ignition: it decreases from 150 to 200 Td and then increases from 200 to 300 Td leading to an optimum reduced electric field for ignition around 200 Td. The different trend observed in this work could be caused by multi-dimensional effects such as the discharge propagation leading to a different spatial density function \mathcal{F} or induced hydrodynamic effects. Another observed feature is the non-monotonic behaviour of the ignition delay time against the equivalence ratio for $\phi \in [0.6, 1]$ with a minimum occurring at $\phi < 1$. These two behaviours could be further analysed by mean of detailed kinetic simulations or even simplified multi-dimensional simulations, which is out of the scope of this work focusing on the comparison between detailed simulations and models (Section 4.3).

τ_{ig}		E/N [Td]		
		150	200	250
ϕ	0.6	635 μs	682 μs	842 μs
	0.8	396 μs	428 μs	470 μs
	1.0	406 μs	438 μs	487 μs

Table 10: Ignition delay times for the different cases of Tab. 8 using fully coupled plasma-assisted combustion simulations.

4.3. Results with the phenomenological model

The PACMIND phenomenological model presented in this work is now compared to the one of [26] and to the results of the detailed plasma-assisted ignition simulations. First in Section 4.3.1, the numerical setup used for the phenomenological model is presented. Then the results for the reference case EN200_ ϕ 08 is presented in Section 4.3.2. Finally, the results on all the cases are summarised in Section 4.3.3.

4.3.1. Numerical setup with the phenomenological models

In this section, the Castela [26] and PACMIND phenomenological models are used to simulate the pin-pin ignition performed with the fully coupled AVBP-PAC solver in Section 4.2. As the plasma phase is not modelled, a fine resolution of the inter-electrode gap is not required and only a coarse mesh with a 15 μm is used. The PACMIND model parameters are computed following the procedure described in Section 3.2.1 for the different mixture compositions, gas temperature and reduced electric field of Tab. 8. The resulting parameters are given in Tab. 11 for the nine cases considered.

The energy deposition \dot{E}^p is locally constant within the interval [0,20] ns and its spatial distribution follows the normalised discharge energy density $\mathcal{F}(x, r) = e^p(x, r)/E^p$ taken from the fully coupled simulation.

4.3.2. Reference case EN200_ ϕ 08

The reference case EN200_ ϕ 08 is first considered to assess and compare the predictive capacities of the two phenomenological models. Figure 20 shows the

	α_1	α_2	α_3	α_4	α_5	α_6	α_7	α_{heat}	α_{vib}
EN150_φ06	0.294	0.0153	0.0033	0.061	0.0	0.0	0.0093	0.288	0.327
EN200_φ06	0.318	0.0299	0.0058	0.073	0.0	0.0	0.0107	0.347	0.214
EN250_φ06	0.314	0.0440	0.0078	0.076	0.0	0.0	0.0111	0.382	0.164
EN150_φ08	0.277	0.0149	0.0031	0.077	0.0	0.0	0.0114	0.293	0.322
EN200_φ08	0.297	0.0289	0.0055	0.091	0.0	0.0	0.0131	0.352	0.211
EN250_φ08	0.292	0.0427	0.0075	0.095	0.0	0.0	0.0135	0.385	0.162
EN150_φ10	0.262	0.0144	0.0030	0.091	0.0	0.0	0.0131	0.297	0.318
EN200_φ10	0.279	0.0281	0.0053	0.108	0.0	0.0	0.0150	0.355	0.208
EN250_φ10	0.274	0.0414	0.0072	0.113	0.0	0.0	0.0154	0.388	0.160

Table 11: PACMIND model parameters for the different plasma-assisted ignition cases considered in this work (see Tab. 8).

gas temperature profiles along the centerline at various stages of the ignition. First at $t = 0.1 \mu\text{s}$ in Fig. 20a, two hot regions are formed close to the electrode tips ($x = \pm 2 \text{ mm}$) for all simulations. For both phenomenological models, the gas temperature is slightly overestimated in these regions. However, a very good agreement between the PACMIND model and the coupled simulation is observed outside of these two small zones. On the contrary, the Castela model predicts a lower temperature almost everywhere along the centerline. Then at $t = 1 \mu\text{s}$, the gas temperature using the PACMIND model tends toward the results of the coupled simulation whereas the observations made at $t = 0.1 \mu\text{s}$ remain valid for the Castela model with a temperature error around 200 K. At $t = 10 \mu\text{s}$ in Fig. 20c, the hydrodynamic effects are clearly visible in the Castela simulation for which the temperature peak is substantially detached from the electrode tips. This effect is less pronounced in the coupled and PACMIND simulations. At $t = 100 \mu\text{s}$ in Fig. 20d, the two hot kernels previously described in Fig. 19d are convected toward the center of the domain. The electrode tip regions are filled with fresh gases and reach a temperature as low as 700 K, highlighting the importance of the gas cooling induced by the hydrodynamic effect. For both the coupled and PACMIND simulations, the two kernels merged at $t \simeq 250 \mu\text{s}$ as shown in Fig. 20e whereas this phenomenon happens at $t \simeq 430 \mu\text{s}$ in the Castela simulation. Finally, all the simulations converge toward a uniform flat

temperature profile around 2000 K as shown in Fig. 20f at $t = 900 \mu\text{s}$.

Figure 20: Comparison of one dimensional profiles along the centerline at different instants of the EN200_φ08 ignition case. The cathode and anode tips are respectively located at $x = -2$ mm and $x = 2$ mm. (---) Reference AVBP-PAC (—) AVBP Castela and (- - -) AVBP PACMIND.

The time evolution of the gas temperature at probe 3 close to the anode tip (*i.e.*, at $(x, r) = (1.75, 0)$ mm) is shown in Fig. 21a. During the first few nanoseconds, an ultra fast gas heating occurs similarly for all simulations. Then, when the energy deposition is switched off in the phenomenological models ($t = 20$ ns), the temperature continues to rise in the PACMIND simulation in agreement with the detailed simulation due to the rapid chemical reactions between radicals. The following temperature dynamic is also well reproduced by our model. As mentioned previously, the hydrodynamic effect is a key aspect of plasma-assisted ignition in this configuration. Our model can well reproduce the axial velocity dynamics in the anode region where the velocity reaches values as high

as $200 \text{ m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$ as shown in Fig. 21b. Finally, our model can accurately reproduce the evolution of key combustion species such as CO as shown in Fig. 21c.

Figure 21: Time evolution of (a) temperature, (b) velocity and (c) CO mass fraction for the EN200_φ08 case at the probe 3. Comparison between (---) Reference AVBP-PAC, (—) AVBP Castela and (- - -) AVBP PACMIND.

The evolution of important quantities were also monitored in the middle of the gap as shown in Fig. 22. In Fig. 22a, our model exhibits the same temperature trend as in the coupled simulation. Regarding the ignition delay time defined by Eq. 55, our model predicts a value of $420 \mu\text{s}$ which is only 2% faster than the coupled simulation. However, the Castela model predicts an ignition time of $597 \mu\text{s}$, which is almost 40% higher than the detailed simulation. A significant difference between the models is observed regarding the vibrational energy loading as shown in Fig. 22b. Thanks to its detailed modeling, the PACMIND model is able to give a good estimate of the vibrational energy peak compared to the coupled simulation. Moreover, due to the better prediction of the radical production, the vibrational energy decay is similar between the PACMIND model and the detailed simulation. Indeed, the evolution of O, CH_3 and OH radicals during the pulse and the afterglow ($t \in [0, 10] \mu\text{s}$) is well reproduced by our model as shown in Figs. 22c, 22d and 22e. As already observed in [33, 20], the methane dissociation during the pulse significantly accelerates the atomic oxygen decay which cannot be described by the Castela model. Finally,

it is important to notice that our model includes the description of NO formation due to the discharge which cannot be predicted by the Castela model. A good agreement is found for the PACMIND model compared to the detailed simulation as shown in Fig. 22f, thus validating the simplified modeling proposed for the NO formation.

Figure 22: Time evolution of selected quantities of the EN200_φ08 case at probe 1. Comparison between (---) Reference AVBP-PAC (—) AVBP Castela and (- - -) AVBP PACMIND.

4.3.3. All cases results

The results of the phenomenological models are now compared for all cases of Tab. 8 to the detailed simulation results of Tab. 10, using the parameters of Tab. 11 for the PACMIND model. The obtained ignition delay times are given in Tab. 12a and Tab. 12b for the Castela and PACMIND models, respectively. For both models, the overall trends are recovered: the ignition delay time

increases with E/N and has a non-monotonic behaviour with the equivalence ratio. In all cases, the Castela model exhibits slower ignition with a minimum of 23% difference in the EN150_φ08 case. In case EN150_φ10, the Castela model predicts an ignition delay time 70% higher than in the detailed simulation. This error is even higher in the EN200_φ06 and EN250_φ06 cases where the ignition takes more than 2 ms to occur. Based on these results, it is not possible to establish recommendations for the use of the Castela model. Indeed, there is no clear trends regarding the error against the equivalence ratio or the reduced electric field. The PACMIND results of Tab. 12b show a good prediction of the ignition delay times, with a maximum error of 7% for the EN250_φ06 case.

		E/N [Td]		
		150	200	250
ϕ	0.6	787 μs (+24%)	≥ 2 ms	≥ 2 ms
	0.8	487 μs (+23%)	597 μs (+39%)	619 μs (+32%)
	1.0	698 μs (+72%)	616 μs (+41%)	640 μs (+31%)

(a) Castela model

		E/N [Td]		
		150	200	250
ϕ	0.6	619 μs (-3%)	651 μs (-5%)	785 μs (-7%)
	0.8	391 μs (-1%)	420 μs (-2%)	452 μs (-4%)
	1.0	411 μs (+1%)	429 μs (-2%)	465 μs (-5%)

(b) PACMIND model

Table 12: Ignition delay times for the different cases of Tab. 8 using (a) the Castela model and (b) the PACMIND model. Relative difference is computed with the reference ignition delay times from Tab. 10.

To characterize the ignition kernels, their sizes have been evaluated by estimating the hot gases area (*i.e.*, a surface in 2D) S_{flame} in the (x, r) plane, plotted in Fig. 23. The kernel size is calculated as the area of the inner temperature iso-surface at 1500 K:

$$S_{\text{flame}} = \int_S \mathcal{H}(T - 1500) \, dS \quad (56)$$

where \mathcal{H} is the Heaviside function.

At $\phi = 1.0$ (see Fig. 23b), the kernel size evolution is similar for all simulations and the differences are in agreement with the ignition delay time errors. However significant discrepancies are observed at $\phi = 0.6$ with the Castela model as shown in Fig. 23a. At $E/N = 150$ Td, the kernel size is lower up to 0.3 ms and then reaches a value similar to the detailed simulation. At higher reduced electric field, the kernel size increases very slowly, leading to the extremely long ignition delays. This difference is due to the anode kernel extinction, visible in Fig. 24 for case EN200_ ϕ 06.

Figure 23: Comparison of the kernel size in the plane (x,r) . (---) Reference AVBP-PAC (—) AVBP Castela and (- - -) AVBP PACMIND. Symbols correspond to the different reduced electric field: ● $E/N = 150$ Td, ▲ $E/N = 200$ Td and ★ $E/N = 250$ Td. The results at $\phi = 0.8$ are very similar to those at $\phi = 1$.

4.4. Expected gains in computational cost

The phenomenological model presented in this work is expected to reduce significantly the computational cost of plasma-assisted combustion simulations. First, the model does not require to solve the Poisson equation and charged species transport equations. Second, smaller chemical mechanisms are needed, typically with 20 species instead of 40 to 60 species required for detailed simulations, thus directly dividing the computational cost by at least two. More

Figure 24: Temperature maps at 100 and 500 μs of the EN200_ ϕ 06 case for the detailed AVBP-PAC simulation (top), the PACMIND model (middle) and the Castela model (bottom).

importantly, coarser meshes could be used when using a model instead of simulating the plasma itself, as for instance in [61, 30, 29]. In this work during the inter-pulse period, the cell size was 15 μm in the plasma region, whereas it could be increased to 50-100 μm when using the model. In 3D, it could result in $(50/15)^3 \simeq 40$ times less cells, a Fourier time-step multiplied by $(50/15)^2 \simeq 10$ and a CFL time-step multiplied by $\simeq 3$. Additionally, CFL and Fourier conditions are not related anymore to the fast and diffuse electrons. At the end, a gain of about two orders of magnitude is expected between a detailed simulation and one with the phenomenological model. Thanks to this lower computational cost, the model can then describe the effects of NRP discharge in very large-size configurations for which detailed plasma simulations are out of reach, and probably not feasible for the years to come.

5. Conclusions

In this work, the phenomenological PACMIND model for NRP discharges in air and methane-air mixtures has been presented. It is an extension of the Castela model [26] to take into account all important species by considering $P \in \mathbb{N}^*$ plasma reactions. The PACMIND approach consists in pre-calculating $P + 2$ parameters α_j , α_{heat} and α_{vib} with detailed kinetic simulations, and tabulate them as functions of the reduced electric field E/N , the equivalence ratio ϕ and a progress variable.

The improvements provided by the PACMIND model have been evaluated on NRP discharges in air and ignitable methane-air mixtures. Validation was made by comparing with experiment in the air case, while comparison with a multi-dimensional fully coupled plasma-combustion simulation was performed for the methane-air mixture. By including more plasma processes and tabulating the model coefficient against judicious parameters, the PACMIND model improves both the kinetic and the fast gas heating predictions. It allows to well reproduce the ignition process in all tested cases with less than 7% error on the ignition delay time. A detailed analysis showed that the global discharge energy branching (α_{chem} , α_{heat} , α_{vib}) do not vary much in fresh and burnt gas in a 1D laminar flame, only the chemical processes α_j change. In addition, the PACMIND model is able to give a good estimate of the NO production, which is critical to optimise PAC systems while keeping the NOx emissions as low as possible. The approach of the PACMIND model may be now extended to discharges in any kind of mixtures, provided that the plasma processes to be included are known.

The simple phenomenological PACMIND model developed in this work may

be easily implemented and used in Large-Eddy Simulations (LES) of 3D turbulent combustion configurations with or without discharges in burnt gas [13] without introducing any significant additional computational cost. Indeed, only one transport equation is added to the standard system, needed for the calculation of the non-equilibrium vibrational energy. Moreover, most of the species considered in the kinetic description of the model are included in reduced chemical mechanisms such as Analytically Reduced Chemistry (ARC) [59], which make the kinetics affordable for LES.

Model parameters availability

The model parameters are not given exhaustively as they depend on various parameters. They can be generated by the corresponding author upon request.

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